

DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE AMONG STUDENTS**Xakimova Malika**Assistant-teacher at TSTU Almalyk branch
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Great opportunities for linguistic and mental development of students involve teaching the grammar of the second language, which contributes to the general education of students, enriches them with knowledge of the fundamental rules, language means of expressing thoughts, assists the development of logical thinking of students, is the basis for the formation of practical skills: speech and spelling. Morphological knowledge, skills and abilities are basic for the formation of linguistic, linguistic and communicative competence.

Nowadays, the term competence is used in various ways. Linguistic competence is a term that was introduced by Chomsky. According to Chomsky (1965), linguistic competence is people's knowledge of language (grammar, syntax, vocabulary) while linguistic performance is using the knowledge in language in real situations. Linguistic competence is identifying the correct grammar, syntax, and vocabulary of a language. Linguistic competence asks: What words do I use? How do I put them into phrases and sentences? Venema (2002) clarified and explained that linguistic competence has been used to describe the multifaceted skills required for the effective use of language. Linguistic competence has long been the desired outcome of second language classrooms. Many researches, such as that done by Kasanga (1996) Pica, Lincoln-Porter, Paninos, and Linnell (1996), and Salaberry (1997), have shown that as opportunities to use the language in meaningful situations increases, so does the acquisition of the second language. Kagan (1995), claimed that language acquisition is fostered by output that is functional and communicative, frequent, redundant, and consistent with the identity of the speaker. Cooperative learning is the ideal situation for communicative output. Language is best acquired when it is used in a way that is meaningful to the student. Cooperative learning provides opportunities for students to express themselves in a functional manner which is personally relevant to them. Students are using the language for a specific purpose, usually to meet certain group goals.

The formation of linguistic competence is carried out using three types of educational activity: receptive, consisting in the perception of material proposed in a finished form; reproductive, associated with the memorization of acquired knowledge or the development of skills and expressed in the reproduction of

knowledge or educational activities; productive, or creative, aimed at self-acquisition of knowledge.

Linguistic competence refers to a person's grammatical competence when producing written communication. Linguistic competence relates to the understanding of [grammar](#), vocabulary, and syntax. This includes punctuation, spelling, and pronunciation as well. This style of communicative competence is mainly used in schools; students need to know the rules that govern word formation, tenses, sound interactions, collocations, word phrase and meaning, and [sentence structure](#) in order to pass most English classes. [Syntax](#), [semantics](#), [phonology](#), and phonetics are additional aspects of linguistic competence. To construct grammatically correct sentences, people need to have at least a low-level mastery of each of these aspects.

Lehmann theorized that linguistic competence plays an important role both in professional life and in the disciplines concerned with the professional personality such as sociology, pedagogy, psychology, and personnel management. Competence is defined in linguistic theory as a person's knowledge of his language, the system of rules which a language user has mastered production and understanding of an infinite number of sentences and recognition of grammatical errors and ambiguities. It is equated to grammatical competence which encompasses "knowledge of lexical items and of rules of morphology, syntax, sentence grammar, semantics and pragmatics" or the competence associated with mastery of the code of a language.

The notion of 'competence' has its basis outside linguistics. It plays an important role both in professional life and in disciplines concerned with the professional personality such as sociology, pedagogy, psychology, and personnel management. Competence is essentially acquired through practice and experience. It is assessed according to some established standard. In psychology, a distinction is made between personal and professional competencies. A person's linguistic competence is part of his personality. On the other hand, it is certainly one of those personal competencies that are highly relevant to professional life [Lehmann, 2009].

The successful implementation of the competence approach can be judged by the extent to which students with their foreign language training are ready to withstand competition in the free labor market in the future and take a worthy place not only in their society, but also in the international community. The competence approach in teaching foreign languages only partially corresponds to the content of communicative competence. Competence is a complex personal

resource that provides an opportunity for effective interaction with the outside world with the help of appropriate competencies. The competence approach opens up opportunities for better preparation of students for real life, including knowledge of the subject, the implementation of productive activities and the actualization of their personal resources. When describing the level of language proficiency achieved because of training. Linguistic competence enables students to produce accurate spoken and written language as well as helping them improve their receptive skills.

Thus, the main purpose of teaching a foreign language is the formation of competences. In the modern educational paradigm, the competence approach is a priority methodological basis for the development of goals, objectives, and content of professional training of future specialists. This has led to the high theoretical and practical significance of the development of the problem of competence, the concept of which is associated with a certain field of activity.

References:

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